

EFFECT OF WARP KNITTING CONDITION ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF NON-CRIMP FABRIC REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF) have been used as reinforcements for composite materials. In NCF, unidirectional fibers can be laid-up and fixed in certain fiber direction according to the requirement by using warp knitting technique. Various research works for NCF composites have been studied, however warp knitting condition on mechanical properties have not been investigated. In this study, differences of warp knitting structure and tension on the structure of NCF and mechanical properties on NCF composites were investigated. Tricot and combination as a knitting structure, and different knitting tension was chosen for the fabrication of NCF.

1 INTRODUCTION

NCF is one of the textile used for the Fiber Reinforced Plastics (FRP) as a reinforcement. In NCF, unidirectional fibers can be stacked and fixed in certain fiber direction according to the requirement by using warp knitting technique. Reinforcing fiber bundles can be straightly aligned with no crimping unlike woven fabrics, FRP with NCF have superior mechanical properties compared to the FRP with other textile. Therefore, the FRP have been used for various large structural body such as the body of ships, blade of wind turbine, and so on because of its high mechanical properties, better impregnation properties of resin, compared to other textiles for reinforcements. Various research works for NCF composites have been studied, and effects of warp knitting yarns on mechanical properties of NCF composites have been one of the main theme for the research works for NCF composites[1]. However, warp knitting condition and warp knitting structures during fabrication of NCF on mechanical properties of the composite materials have not been investigated so far. In this study, differences of warp knitting structure and warp knitting condition especially tension of the knitting yarns on the structure of NCF and mechanical properties of NCF composites were investigated. Two kinds of knitting structure called "Combination" and "Tricot" as a knitting structure, and different knitting tension was chosen for the fabrication of NCF.

2 REINFORCEMENT, FABRICATION AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

First, the differences of knitting structure in NCF used in this study is explained. Fig.1 shows the picture of NCF with knitting structure of "Combination" and "Tricot" with reinforcing fiber bundle in 0 and 90 degrees. In this picture, crosswise direction is corresponding to processing direction of NCF. Glass fibers, and polyester resin fibers were used for reinforcing fibers and knitting yarns respectively. The difference between the combination and the tricot is simply the density of knitting. In tricot, the knitting yarn is crossed over 0 ° fibers obliquely in each time when weft fiber bundles were inserted. On the other hand, the knitting yarn is crossed over 0 ° fibers obliquely in each time when weft fiber bundles were inserted.

Therefore, the tricot is higher in knitting yarn density over the 0 ° direction fibers. In this study, the effects of these two knitting structure and the difference of tension.

Table 1 showed the details of 4 kinds of NCFs with 0° and 90° reinforcing fibers with photographs of appearance of each textile. The upper two fabrics are NCF with the structure of combination and the lower two were that with tricot structure. Each NCF with different knitting structure were fabricated with higher and lower tension of the knitting yarns. The higher and lower tension of about 1.8cN and

7cN were chosen in this study. The mass per unit area of these four NCFs were the same. These four reinforcements were named as Cw, Cs, Tw, and Ts respectively in this study. In these names, “C” and “T” represented Combination and Tricot structure, and “s” and “w” represented knitting tension of strong and weak.

Fig.1 Differences in knitting structure

Table 1 Detail of reinforcements

Name	Structure /Tension	Weight of fiber (g/m ²)	Appearance
Cw	Combination Weak: 1.8cN	Warp: 480 Weft: 480 Total: 960	
Cs	Combination Strong: 7.0cN	Warp: 480 Weft: 480 Total: 960	
Tw	Tricot Weak: 1.8cN	Warp: 480 Weft: 480 Total: 960	
Ts	Tricot Strong: 7.0cN	Warp: 480 Weft: 480 Total: 960	

In this research, FRP boards were fabricated using hand lay-up forming method using these NCFs. Unsaturated polyester resin was used as a base material. The laminated structure was symmetrical 0/90. After resin impregnation, pressure of 3.3 kPa was applied and cured at room temperature for 12 h and 100 ° C for 2 h. In order to clarify the difference in internal structure of the fabricated FRP board, cross section was observed and a tensile test was carried out. The tensile test was conducted using a universal testing machine, with a distance between chucks of 100 mm and a test speed of 1 mm / min.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Effect of knitting condition on structure of reinforcing fiber bundle

The influence of the difference in warp knitting structure on the mechanical properties of NCF was investigated. First, the thickness of the molded specimen was measured and the fiber volume fraction (Vf) of the specimen was calculated from the value and the fineness of the reinforcement. The values are shown in Fig.2. From this result, Vf of each specimen was different despite the same molding condition. Vf of the specimen using the reinforcement with combination structure was larger than that with tricot structure, and in combination specimens and the tricot specimens respectively, Vf is lower in the specimen with the high knitting yarn tension.

Fig.2 Volume fraction in each specimen

Next, the cross-sectional shape of 0 ° fiber bundle was quantified. Observation of the cross section was carried out, and the width and thickness of 0° fiber bundle cross section were measured. The results are shown in Fig.3. From this result, the cross section of the 0° fiber bundle was flatter in the combination specimen and the thicker in the tricot specimen. Also, there is almost no influence of tension in the combination specimen, however, the higher the tension is, the thicker in the thickness direction of 0° fiber bundle in tricot specimen.

From the these results, in the tricot specimen with higher density of knitting yarns, the cross section of the fiber bundle became close to a circle because of the stronger force for binding the fiber bundles. As a result, the thickness was thicker and the Vf was lower in the case of tricot structure and larger tension of knitting yarns.

Fig.3 Cross-sectional shape of 0 degree fiber bundles

3.2 Tensile test

Figure 4 and 5 show the results of elastic modulus and strength obtained by the tensile test. Comparing the elastic modulus of the combination test piece and the tricot test piece, the combination specimens showed higher values. In addition, comparing with the strength of tension, the tricot specimens showed almost the same value, and the combination specimen with lower knitting tension showed higher tensile strength. Since this result is similar to the tendency of Vf, the effect of Vf seems to be larger. On the other hand, comparing the strengths, Cs, Tw, and Ts show almost the same values, and Cw was lower than those values. From these results,

Fig.4 Tensile modulus

Fig.5 Tensile strength

Next, the elastic modulus and the strength were calculated again assuming V_f is the same for excluding the effect due to the difference in V_f . These results were shown in Fig.6 and 7. Comparing the elastic modulus of the combination specimen and the tricot specimen, the tricot showed higher values than the combination, contrary to the previous result. In comparison with the difference of the knitting tension, the specimen with higher tension exhibited a higher value in both the combination and the tricot specimens. On the other hand, in the case of the tensile strength, as with the elastic modulus results, tricot shows higher values than the combination, and in comparison with the difference of the knitting tension, the specimen with higher tension showed a higher value in both the combination and the tricot specimens. Since the difference in V_f does not affect this result, the differences in fiber orientation would cause this differences in the result. Therefore, in order to investigate the difference in fiber orientation, the local meandering of the fibers in plane in detail. Cross-sectional observation was performed to quantify the fiber orientation angle. Fig.8 and 9 showed the relationship between elastic modulus and fiber orientation and the relationship between strength and fiber orientation. From these results, both the elastic modulus and the strength decreased with increase in the fiber orientation angle in each of the combination and tricot specimens. Comparing the combination and tricot specimens, tricot specimens showed high values for both modulus and strength.

Fig.6 Tensile modulus calculated again assuming V_f is the same

Fig.7 Tensile strength calculated again assuming V_f is the same

Fig.8 Relationship between tensile modulus and crimp angle

Fig.9 Relationship between tensile strength and crimp angle

4 CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The effect of knitting yarn structure and knitting tension on the structure of reinforcing fiber and the mechanical properties of FRP reinforced by NCF was clarified.
- 2) Mechanical properties can be determined by designing the pitch of reinforcing fibers in addition to the above design elements.

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